

**DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION IN THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN****SAYDASOVA CHAROSKHON KARIMKHANOVNA***TASHKENT CITY DEPARTMENT OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION OF
MIRABAD DISTRICT DIRECTOR OF THE STATE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION
ORGANIZATION NO. 174.*

Annotation: The democratic and developing state headed by the president was well aware that the hopes for the future are connected with the younger generation, therefore, to the people and society, the head of state proposed a program radically reforming the entire education system. In full compliance with the National Training Program, education in the country is implemented in the following types: preschool, general secondary, specialized secondary, vocational education, higher, post-university education, advanced training and retraining of personnel, extracurricular education. The main feature of the program is the continuity of education. Everyone has the opportunity to acquire knowledge, professional skills and specialties throughout their lives.

Keywords: national culture, number of children

Ensuring the intellectual, personal and physical development of the child; - Implementation of the necessary correction of deviations in the development of the child; - Introducing children to national culture and universal values; - Preparing children for school. According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of normative legal acts in the field of preschool education", children aged 2 to 6-7 years are admitted to a preschool institution by the admission committee at the departments of methodological support and organization of activities of public education institutions established by the decision of the khokimiyats of districts (cities), taking into account the relevant medical opinion.

The admissions committee may also, on an exceptional basis, accept out of turn children whose parents have provided charitable assistance in strengthening the material and technical base of the preschool institution. The contingent of such children should not exceed 20% of the total planned capacity of a preschool institution. Also, according to this provision, the number of groups in a preschool institution is determined by the founder based on the capacity of the institution and the planned occupancy of groups. In a group from 2 to 3 years old there should be at least 15, but not more than 20 children, from 3 to 6-7 years old — at least 20, but not more than 25 children. And the school year in a preschool institution begins on September 2 of each year, ends on June 1 of the following year and the wellness period begins before the start of the school year.

Kindergartens in Uzbekistan have everything necessary for the upbringing and education of children. In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the largest number of kindergartens falls on the city of Nukus (15%), Amudarya (12%) and Beruniysky (11%) districts. (Fig. 2) All the features are taken into account when opening a kindergarten, which are checked by various authorities. But in recent years, the birth rate of the population has increased, so there are currently not enough places in kindergartens. Young parents are forced to stay at home with their child, unable to go to work. Many are trying to get out on their own, turning to their grandparents for help. Undoubtedly, close relatives have a beneficial effect on the child, but without having a professional skill, they cannot teach the child.

Thus, in our opinion, one of the solutions to this problem is the opening of private preschool educational institutions, that is, kindergartens. Depending on the location and conditions of detention, the number of children in these kindergartens can range from 5 to 15 children. Such a number of children determines the employment of the population and the possibilities of quality child care. For example, if 7 children will be brought up in a kindergarten, then in order for them to be in favorable conditions, it is necessary to involve three people. Under favorable conditions, this institution can expand. And at the same time, the issue of the lack of

places in kindergartens is relevant in different countries and each country is struggling with this problem in its own way.

Literatures:

1. Economic and statistical analysis: Textbook for universities./ Edited by prof. S. D. Ilyenkova. — M.: UNITY-DANA, 2002.
2. Economic statistics: Textbook/ Edited by Yu. N. Ivanov. — M.: Infra-M, 2003.
3. Uralbaeva, G. U. Development of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan / G. U. Uralbaeva. — Text : direct // Young scientist. — 2013. — № 10 (57). — Pp. 401-403. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/57/7821> / (accessed: 11/27/2022).